

Bibliometric Analysis and Systematic Literature Review in Management Practices & Artificial Intelligence

Analyse bibliométrique et revue systématique de la littérature sur les pratiques de gestion et l'intelligence artificielle

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative technology to reshape different practices of management, such as decision-making processes, organizational performance, and human interactions in business settings. The purpose of this study is to map out the intersection between Artificial Intelligence and Management practices. Several studies of relevant scholarly articles have been carried out to identify the interaction of AI on the three main Management practices through a comprehensive review analysis using Scopus database. This bibliometric study offers insights into scientific trends, author patterns and thematic field advancement. In addition to pointing out the gaps in the literature and suggesting directions for future research such as the ethical issues surrounding the use of AI. The results of the systematic literature review are eventually mapped out on VOSviewer and presented by visualization techniques demonstrating key research clusters. This study is subject to limitations as it solely depends on the Scopus database. Future studies could grant from merging additional sources like PubMed, Crossref, among others.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence; Management practices; Decision-making; Ethical decision-making; Human relationships.

Résumé

L'intelligence artificielle (IA) s'est imposée comme une technologie transformative pour remodeler différentes pratiques de gestion, telles que les processus de prise de décision, la performance organisationnelle et les interactions humaines dans les contextes commerciaux. L'objectif de cette étude est de cartographier les pratiques de l'intelligence artificielle et de la gestion. Plusieurs études d'articles universitaires pertinents ont été menées pour identifier l'interaction de l'IA sur les trois principales pratiques de gestion à travers une analyse de revue complète via la base de données Scopus. Cette étude bibliométrique offre des perspectives sur les tendances scientifiques, les schémas d'auteurs et l'avancement du champ thématique. En plus de souligner les lacunes dans la littérature et de suggérer des orientations pour des recherches futures telles que les questions éthiques entourant l'utilisation de l'IA. Les résultats de la revue systématique de la littérature sont finalement cartographiés sur VOSviewer et présentés par des techniques de visualisation démontrant des clusters de recherche clés. Cette étude est sujette à des limitations car elle dépend uniquement de la base de données Scopus. Des études futures pourraient bénéficier de la fusion de sources supplémentaires telles que PubMed, Crossref, entre autres.

Mots clés :

Intelligence artificielle ; Pratiques de gestion ; Prise de décision ; Prise de décision éthique ; Relations humaines.

Introduction

Nowadays Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been increasingly integrated into various business contexts worldwide. In fact, AI requires shifting the common conventional Management practices into contemporary Management methods to ultimately adapt to its integration and to ensure operational management flexibility. Artificial intelligence has the power to fundamentally transform the process by which management practices are carried out (Kshetri, 2021). Due to increased processing technology and more sophisticated algorithms, machines can now match or even surpass employees in tasks requiring high cognitive ability in the workplace. Now as a result of the frequent adoption of AI technologies and its influence on the way firms operates, there is a surge need to examine the changes on managerial practices throughout the three main practices namely: decision-making processes, organizational performance and human relationships within companies. A comprehensive study investigated AI application in international businesses, found out that AI was not enough to benefit organizations (Chowdhury et al., 2023). However, this request firstly developing strategies to integrate AI with employees, and focus mainly on human talents, leadership, and teamwork to maintain an innovative business culture.

Management practices represent the sum of methods and strategies managers employ to meet the business goals and boost productivity performance (Ignacio, 2021). Managerial activities involve planning, organizing, leading, and controlling while taking external environment into consideration. Management practices can be classified into three major aspects: decision-making, firm performance, and the dynamics of human relations. A high skilled leader is crucial to establish a positive work environment, a productive team and to ensure these practices are accomplished in line with corporate objectives. However, as cutting-edge technologies become deeply embedded in businesses, managers can no longer depend solely on conventional managerial methods (Pawar & Dhupal, 2024). Thus, to prevent disruptions on operating activities leading entities need to adjust these practices in order to accommodate emerging technologies. One prominent leading technology revolutionizing different business domains is artificial intelligence, that holds a pivotal role in decision-making optimization, improve operational efficiency and enabling adaptive managerial strategies.

What is the application of AI on management practices and what are the key patterns and emerging trends resulting from their interconnection?

As this study seeks to map out Artificial Intelligence and Management practices. The subsequent sections are structured as follows:

The first section is the introduction. Followed by the literature review, representing the most relevant publications from Scopus. Then research methods, that outlines the methodology adopted to systematically review Artificial Intelligence and Management Practices intersection. The next section is results, that delves into the outcomes of our VOSviewer visualizations while the discussion is the following part. The last section, carries out conclusions drawn from the comprehensive bibliometric analysis and the systematic review.

1. Literature review

Several studies into Artificial Intelligence have been conducted to examine diverse perspectives on Artificial Intelligence across numerous fields. The majority of the papers addressing Artificial Intelligence along with Management practices have been published over the last five years, as indicated by Table 1 bellow.

Table N°1: Artificial Intelligence and Management practices research papers results (Scopus)

Author Publication	Title	Focus Area	Journal	Year of Publication	Cite
Nawaz, N., Arunachalam, H., Pathi, B.K. , Gajenderan, V.	The adoption of artificial intelligence in human resources management practices	AI Technologies in Human Resources Management Practices.	International Journal of Information Management Data Insights	2024	2
Buchelt, A. , Adrowitzer, A. , Kieseberg, P. , Stampfer, K. , Holzinger, A.	Exploring artificial intelligence for applications of drones in forest ecology and management	Emergency Management for infrastructure	Forest Ecology and Management	2024	7

Oduro, S. , De Nisco, A. , Mainolfi, G.	Do digital technologies pay off? A meta-analytic review of the digital technologies/firm performance nexus	AI and firm performance	Technovation	2023	5
Bhardwaj, B. , Sharma, D. , Dhiman, M.C.	AI and emotional intelligence for modern business management	Management	AI and Emotional Intelligence for Modern Business Management	2023	17
Rai, A. , Singh, L.B.	Artificial Intelligence-based People Analytics Transforming Human Resource Management Practices	Human Resource Management	The Adoption and Effect of Artificial Intelligence on Human Resources Management	2023	3
Lin, S. , Döngül, E.S. , Uygun, S.V. , ... Huy, D.T.N. , Tuan, P.V.	Exploring the Relationship between Abusive Management, Self-Efficacy and Organizational Performance in the Context of Human–Machine Interaction Technology and Artificial Intelligence with the Effect of Ergonomics	Business	Sustainability 2022	2022	19

Díaz, L.E.C. , Abreu, A.A. , Estevez, P.G. , Pires, S.R.I.	An empirical study on supply chain management practices within the hotel segment in Spain using an artificial intelligence technique	Hospitality Industry	International Journal of Services and Operations Management	2021	3
Lee, H.	Role of artificial intelligence and enterprise risk management to promote corporate entrepreneurship and business performance: evidence from korean banking sector	Banking sector	Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems	2020	10
Maity, S.	Identifying opportunities for artificial intelligence in the evolution of training and development practices	Human Resource Development	Journal of Management Development	2019	66

Source : Scopus

This review consists of carried empirical studies emphasizing on inquiring the contribution of artificial intelligence into transforming managerial practices in various sectors such as banking, infrastructure, hospitality, ecology, etc. Additionally, it was noted that the majority of these publications addressed the ways in which AI promotes organizational performance and supports business decision systems. The findings of these comprehensive studies serve to assist managers make informed decisions, and adapt their managerial procedures before implementing AI into business operations.

According to Herbert Simon's Decision-Making Theory, employees never take an optimal decision, instead they end up selecting the most satisfactory solution only (Lee, 2020). This can be due to the constraints of time, limited knowledge or unavailability of data. He argues, that there will be always a favorable option neglected by decision makers. This theory goes in line with the incorporation of AI into managerial practices since AI can generate a large amount of data at a very rapid pace that will result on an overload and confusion among managers. This research literature investigates the way these restrictions are represented in management practices and AI, highlighting the strategies used by policy makers to overcome the challenges associated with decision-making. Another theory "Sociotechnical Systems" developed by Eric Trist and Fred Emery in the 1950s, underlines the intersection between the human aspect and the technical element when addressing organizational processes. (Abbas & Michael, 2023). It suggests that raising the performance of an organization is highly related to the interplay between tools (technology) and people (employees) taking into consideration the business culture. The proposed theory, is pertinent to our analysis as it offers a framework to recognize the effect of AI adoption on social structures. Looking into how these relationships are reviewed in the literature serve in demonstrating the new trends related to execution of AI in management.

2. Research Methods

2.1. Data Sources (Scopus)

Using bibliometric analytic tools, the current study attempts to gain insight into the literature on Artificial Intelligence and Management practices. Bibliometric analysis refers to the adoption of statistical methods to quantitatively analyze research data extracted from bibliographic articles, books or journals. This technique is usually applied to examine journal citations to scientific publications, and classify papers according to research areas. Data for this study will be sourced from Scopus database while relying on the keywords feature for our main

terms: Artificial Intelligence and Management practices. Scopus refers to a comprehensive database of publications with peer review that include conference papers, scientific books and journals developed by Elsevier, a scholarly publisher in 2004.

2.2. Research Methods (VOSviewer)

For an in-depth examination of the systematic literature review from Scopus database, bibliometric data analysis requires specialized tool. Namely, VOSviewer, which is one kind of software designed to assist this particular procedure. It allows recognizing prominent research institutions within a certain area, the graphic visualization of publication patterns across time, and the identification of notable authors. The visualized findings are characterized by their visibility to enable an easy interpretation.

The initial search for "Artificial Intelligence" AND "Management practices" yielded a total of 687 documents across various domains. To narrow down our search parameters, we restricted the subject areas to include Business, Management and Accounting, Social Sciences, Decision Sciences, Economics, Econometrics, and Finance. Additionally, we limited the publication years from 2019 to 2024, reflecting the focus on the most recent five-year period. As a result, the number of documents founded reduced 452 and eventually the total number of retrieved papers was 79 after selecting only papers with "open access". The figure 1 below is a diagram illustrating the main steps taken.

Figure N°1: Scopus data selection process

Source : Authors

VOSviewer refers to a software serves for developing and displaying visualization for bibliometric networks. These networks can be generated with several types of associations, including citation, co-citation, bibliographic coupling, co-occurrence, or co-authorship, as represented in figure 2, and they may consist of a variety of elements, like scientific, articles, journals, publications or authors. Co-authorship is when two or more writers work together through collaboration or directly across the same network. In particular, co-occurrence describes the appearance of two keywords together. The connections between journals are indicated by citations, which occur when researchers of one paper cite researchers of another. When a third publication mentions two articles simultaneously, it is referred to as co-citation. On the other hand, bibliographic coupling emphasizes on the similarities in the journals' reference lists.

Figure N°2: VOSviewer bibliometric networks

Source : Authors

3. Results

3.1. Co- authorship analysis: Unit of analysis “authors”

Table N°2: Co- authorship analysis from VOSviewer

ID	Author	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
138	jiang, yangyang	1	523	1
272	wen, jun	1	523	1
7	afaq, anam	1	96	3
74	dwivedi, yogesh kumar	1	96	3
100	gaur, loveleen	1	96	3
240	singh, gurmeet	1	96	3
142	kamariotou, maria	1	87	1
148	kitsios, fotis	1	87	1
55	christ, oliver	1	75	4
104	giermindl, lisa marie	1	75	4
159	leicht-deobald, ulrich	1	75	4
218	redzepe, abduallah	1	75	4
250	strich, franz	1	75	4
32	bag, surajit	1	73	3

Source: Vosviewer

The table above represents the Co-authorship Analysis for authors, including the 10 most cited authors retrieved from VOSviewer. The results demonstrate collaborations of combined authors in research works. As these articles have been published in the recent five years at the same time are highly cited, this typically indicates the significant influence within the relevant field of work. Regarding the total link strength tab, it shows how strongly a particular researcher is linked to other scholars as co-authors overall.

Figure N°3: Network visualization of authors co-authorship analysis from VOSviewer

Source: Vosviewer

The finding of the co-authorship analysis revealed a total number of 45 unconnected authors, from which only 10 were strongly connected and demonstrated through the visualization in the graph above. Meaning those authors combined their knowledge and expertise and have made a significant contribution in our field of research.

3.2. Co-occurrence analysis: Unit of analysis “all keywords”

Figure N°4: Network visualization of co-occurrence analysis for keywords from VOSviewer

Source: Vosviewer

Keywords are shown as nodes in the network graph above, and the connections between them show co-occurrence associations. Keywords that are more important or common in the dataset are typically represented by larger or more central nodes. In this case, “artificial intelligence” is the most mentioned keyword from the overall database in different research areas, which reveals that it is a trendy term adopted in recent works. Followed by keywords associated to management practices, decision support systems, sustainability and information management, which are demonstrated in noticeable nodes. In this context, the interconnections between terms frequently employed in papers appear in visualizations of co-occurrence analysis for keywords. Thus, the associated keywords form a cluster in the same color and connects by arcs.

Table N°3: Co- occurrence Analysis: Unit of analysis (All Keywords)

<i>Colors</i>	<i>Clusters</i>	<i>Number of Items</i>	<i>Keyword field</i>
<i>RED</i>	1	45	Digital technologies, regression analysis, firm performance
<i>GREEN</i>	2	38	Human machine interface, Research & Development
<i>BLUE</i>	3	36	Decision-making, data driven decisions, Information systems
<i>YELLOW</i>	4	34	Management practices, water management, big data driven
<i>PURPLE</i>	5	32	Decision-support systems, ability
<i>TURQOISE</i>	6	32	AI methods, clustering algorithms, forestry
<i>ORANGE</i>	7	29	Hospitality industry, hotel management predictive maintenance
<i>BROWN</i>	8	29	Facilities management, data protection, management algorithms
<i>PINK</i>	9	28	Bibliometric analysis, research work, data management
<i>LIGHT RED</i>	10	27	Decision makers, industrial management
<i>LIGHT GREEN</i>	11	26	Uncertainty, healthcare, healthsystems advanced technology
<i>LIGHT BLUE</i>	12	25	Agricultural system, productivity, remote sensing
<i>LIGHT BROWN</i>	13	22	Business intelligence, business models
<i>LIGHT PURPLE</i>	14	22	Artificial intelligence, leadership, organizational culture
<i>TURQOISE</i>	15	22	AI ethics, Software engineering, environmental impact
<i>LIGHT ORANGE</i>	16	21	Ethical AI, AI governance, ethics

<i>LIGHT BROWN</i>	17	21	Electronics equipment, quality 4.0
<i>LIGHT PINK</i>	18	19	Pavement, assessment methods, degradation
<i>GREY</i>	19	18	Crop modeling, crop simulations
<i>LIGHT GREY</i>	20	18	Crack assessment, management, deep learning
<i>GREEN</i>	21	17	Crowd management, simulation model
<i>LIGHT GREY</i>	22	15	Electronic commerce, e-commerce, online retailing
<i>LIGHT GREY</i>	23	14	Accuracy assessment
<i>GREY</i>	24	13	Ecosystems, metadata
<i>LIGHT GREEN</i>	25	12	Chat bot, framework
<i>LIGHT GREY</i>	26	11	IOT, internet
<i>LIGHT GREY</i>	27	9	Digital competencies
<i>LIGHT GREY</i>	28	8	New technologies
<i>GREY</i>	29	4	Knowledge management practice

Source: Vosviewer

Throughout the dataset, clusters are assemblies of associated concepts. The findings of our co-occurrence analysis reveal a total number of 29 clusters represented in different colors as demonstrated in table 3. Each cluster covers a sum of keywords that belong to the same cluster, frequently have meanings that are conceptually similar or tightly connected, called “items”. For instance, cluster 3 (blue cluster) involves 36 items and revolves around “decision-making”, “data driven decisions” and “information systems”. While cluster number 7 in orange, include 29 items covering keywords array of “hospitality industry” and “robotics”, hence mapped in the visualization.

3.3. Co-occurrence analysis: Unit of analysis “countries”

The figure displays two main clusters, each of which represents specific subject focuses and geographical collaborations. Cluster 2 (shown in green) is dominated by the United Kingdom

and India, indicating a focused effort in academic output concerning "artificial intelligence" and "management practices." The United Kingdom stands out as a central node, demonstrating its status as a leading contributor to our research field followed by India. Alternatively, the United States, China, and Hong Kong appear in cluster number 5, which is colored purple, indicating their combined impact on scientific research projects. China stands out among these countries as a prominent hub due to its substantial contribution to the amount of published scientific research

Figure N°5: Network visualization of countries co-occurrence analysis from VOSviewer

Source: Vosviewer

3.4. Citation analysis: Unit of analysis “authors”

In the visualization below the nodes indicate authors, while the arcs demonstrate the citation connections. The citation analysis of authors indicates the frequency in which an author cites another in their scientific publications. Authors who are often cited jointly are forming a common cluster in the same color and appearing next to each other. In this case, the results show five different clusters, “Giermindl, lisa maria” and “choi, hemin” form one common cluster in green, and means that those authors frequently cite each other on their academic research which opens an opportunity for a future collaboration in a shared field on interest to eventually contribute to research through new knowledge.

Figure N°6: Network visualization of authors citation analysis from VOSviewer

Source: Vosviewer

3.5. Citation analysis: Unit of analysis “documents”

The visualization illustrates documents through nodes and citations through links in between. The focus area of this type of analysis is the different patterns of citation of journals, books, articles and conference papers. The formed clusters in red and green represent papers that are frequently cited together highlighting significant subjects in a particular discipline.

Figure N°7: Network visualization of documents citation analysis from VOSviewer

Source: Vosviewer

3.6. Bibliographic coupling analysis: Unit of analysis “countries”

Countries are linked based on shared bibliographies and visually displayed as nodes. This bibliographic coupling of countries is examining the similarities of academic joint endeavors between authors from different countries in terms references they have in common.

The United Kingdom, China, Italy and Poland are represented in separate clusters, strongly linked as they are all sharing the same scope of interest in their publication including similar bibliographies in artificial intelligence and management practices. This opens opportunities for future collaboration internationally to allocate expertise and eventually contribute to significant research fields and come up with new solutions for managers to consider while implementing AI.

Figure N°8: Network visualization of countries Bibliographic coupling analysis from VOSviewer

Source: Vosviewer

3.7. Bibliographic coupling analysis: Unit of analysis “authors”

Bibliographic coupling of authors is similar to the approach of countries, as it emphasizes on common references between authors while showing potential associations in collaboration in shared fields of interests. The nodes clustered together identify authors contributing to the same subject area of research.

Figure N°9: Network visualization of authors Bibliographic coupling analysis from VOSviewer

Source: Vosviewer

3.8. Co-citation analysis: Unit of analysis “references”

The nodes below denote the references and the links connecting them show the degree of strength of the co-citation connection. In this context, co-citation analysis reveals the extent to which references are cited together.

Figure N°10: Network visualization of references Co-citation analysis from VOSviewer

Source: Vosviewer

3.9. Co-citation analysis: Unit of analysis “authors”

The VOSviewer visualization below show the number of times authors are mentioned together in academic documents with the aim of recognizing possible collaboration and joint research interests.

Figure N°11: Network visualization of authors Co-citation analysis from VOSviewer

Source: Vosviewer

4. Discussion

After applying the filter of “subjects”, from 2019 to 2024, the results generated 79 selective publications that demonstrate a growing tendency of published scientific journals among different geographic areas. This research implemented bibliometric analysis to investigate the existing and new trends of artificial intelligence and management practices. This study involves different types of VOSviewer analysis such as co-occurrence, co-authorship, citation, co-citation, and bibliographic coupling. Within the network visualization, the number of publications is denoted through several circles holding different sizes, whereas colors convey the yearly average publication, and arcs represent the level of relationships between nodes. The strongest the relationship is the thickest the arc will be. The findings revealed an array of a well-connected research field. The emergence of significant topic patterns proves the weight of research at the intersection of AI and management practices throughout all types of bibliometric

analysis. One study found that artificial intelligence can be adopted to assist in making quick and efficient decisions, detect complex configurations in a dataset, and anticipate business trends that guide managers in strategic planning (Loso et al., 2022). The co-authorship analysis displayed one dominating cluster involving a large number of authors with strong relationship links. This said, those scholars are closely related when it comes to our research subject. This encourages an exchange of knowledge and allow concerned authors create synergies into academic publications. Then, the co-occurrence analysis of keywords presented several clusters of terms from different industries, yet strongly associated to our research field. The keywords that frequently occurred together were: information management, decision-making, decision support systems, sustainability, digital technologies and artificial intelligence. Also, the citation analysis provided the most cited books, articles and journals that were mainly related to the ethical dilemma when incorporating AI. In fact, acknowledging the occurrence of biases of AI systems is a vital initial action toward addressing ethical issues (Funmilola Olatundun Olatoye et al., 2024). Transparency has to be prioritized as a way to promote trust in artificial intelligence technologies, specifically when it applies to the generation of decision-making procedures and the way they are communicated. While the number of co-cited references addressed mostly AI contribution to organizations as a whole especially supply chain activities. Besides, the advancement of bibliographic coupling of our subject area was highly prominent in China, United Kingdom, Italy and Poland. Business executives can employ the knowledge gained from this research findings to assist AI's revolutionary power to improve performance and accelerate decision-making processes.

Conclusion

To conclude, the intersection of artificial intelligence (AI) and management practices was conducted using bibliometric analysis in VOSviewer and the systematic literature review was carried out through Scopus. This yielded to significant insights into the area of our research. Based on these diligent assessments, we have witnessed a growing and considerable body review in this particular domain. Our findings imply there are more potentials for additional contributions by scholars in the dynamic and growing disciplines of AI and management practices.

According to visualization on keywords co-occurrence analysis, the uses of AI in multiple domains such as sustainability, health, management systems, hospitality and digitalization are one of the prominent outcomes of this study. AI applications in these different disciplines

explain its fundamental role in decision-making systems in general. Also, the various range of keywords commonly related to the term AI uncovers the prevalent adoption of AI-based technologies. With this said, VOSviewer findings allowed us to reveal the considerable existing work contributions and the level to which the two fields are dynamic.

The result of this analysis act as a call to action for future authors to keep carrying on research in this area as it is not yet saturated. There is a high potential to work in new study questions, also, cross-disciplinary collaborations become possible by the continuous rapid advancement of AI and its uses. However, it is imperative to acknowledge limitations of this research. One such limitation is the use of a relatively limited database, gathered via Scopus. Extracting more scientific publications from several databases is one recommendation to allow an enhanced systematic bibliometric study. The expansion of the studied sample may allow academics to explore new trends. Eventually, this will offer decision makers a comprehensive understanding of the connection of two studied terms and will provide alternative solutions to adopt before incorporating AI in their any managerial procedure.

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